

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****DERMATOGLYPHIC PATTERNS OR DESIGNS ON THE
HANDS OF FEMALES SUFFERING FROM BREAST
CANCER**¹Muhammad Abid Owais, ²Dr Hafiz Tyyab Zafar, ³Dr Ammar Ahmad¹Assistant Professor, Surgery Ward Baqai Medical University Karachi²Jinggangshan University, Jiangxi Jian China³Medical officer, Children Hospital Faisalabad**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this research work is to examine the association of the digital dermatoglyphic designs or patterns of the hands of the females with the complication of the breast cancer and females with high danger to develop the breast cancer.

Methodology: We studied the fingerprints of six hundred and sixteen females divided in 3 groups; one hundred and fifty-four patients suffering from breast cancer, one hundred and fifty-four females present with high risk to develop the breast cancer and three hundred and eight females in the healthy control group to compare the patterns with the females with disease or risk of acquiring the complication.

Results: We identified the pattern of six or high digital whorls more commonly in females suffering from breast cancer (48.70%) in comparison with the group of controls (27.50%). This was also more common in the females with high risks of the acquiring the breast cancer (47.40%) in comparison with the group of controls (27.50%). We found no disparities in females with high danger to acquire the breast cancer (47.40%) in comparison with the females present with the complication of the breast cancer (48.70%).

Conclusion: The role of the digital dermatoglyphic is very important in the identification of the females suffering from breast cancer or present with high risk to acquire the breast cancer which can provide the awareness to start the early treatment to prevent the risk of the disease.

KEYWORDS: Breast Cancer, Dermatoglyphic, Complication, Disorder, Association, Suffering, Controls, Pattern, Whorls.

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Please cite this article in press Muhammad Abid Owais et al., *Dermatoglyphic Patterns Or Designs On The Hands Of Females Suffering From Breast Cancer.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(01).

INTRODUCTION:

The diagnosis of the females presents with the enhanced risk to develop the disease of breast cancer and most early probable identification of the patients having breast cancer should recover the outcomes of the treatment of the breast cancer. The vital evidence of the association between a previous history of the breast cancer in the family and development of this complication is present in the records. There is an increase in the prevalence of the breast cancer with the previous history of the disease in the family as

well as in the patients with early start of the menses, delayed menopause and obesity, the reason behind these complications may be the role played by the gene. The evaluation of the genetic identifier is effective to discover the persons present with the high risk of acquiring the disease. The aim of this research work is to assess the association between the dermatoglyphic patterns and the incidence of the breast cancer. Figure-1 describes the major digital identified patterns.

True Whorl

Accidental Loop

Twinned Loop

Figure 1

METHODOLOGY:

The current research work is a transverse study conducted in Surgery Ward Baqai Medical University Karachi from November 2016 to December 2018. We used the ink print fingerprints procedure for all the patients. Code number was in use for the identification of the patients so that categorization of the patterns of the fingerprint carried out in an only single blind fashion. The categorizations of the patients carried out in three groups; Group-1 (n: 154 females), containing the females suffering from breast cancer, Group-2 (n: 154 females), Females present with the enhanced risk of the breast cancer and Group-3 (n: 308 female) contained the females as healthy controls. Females suffering from the breast cancer were present with the histopathologic evidence. We also included the patients with high risk of acquiring the breast cancer according to the standard. These standards include a past history of family for the incidence of the breast cancer in only 1st relatives, or 2 of the mentioned 4 criteria;

1. A previous history of the surgery of breast.
2. Initiation of the menses before 12 year of age.
3. Menopause after fifty year of age.
4. First delivery of the child after thirty year of age.

The members of the group of controls were present with no such risk factors nor the cancer of breasts. The additional needs of the research work included

that increased risk and group of controls were present with a routine examination of the breast in the 2 two year of the digital dermatoglyphic research work. Ware was in use for the recording of the dates and Chi square method was in use of the statistical assessment of the collected information.

RESULTS:

For this series (six hundred and sixteen females), there was important statistically disparities between patterns of six $\leq$ whorls with comparative frequency of 37.80% and patterns of six greater than whorls with comparative frequency of 62.10% per each patient ($X^2 = 27.452$). Additionally, within Group-1, the outcomes of the X^2 test between the patterns of six whorls having comparative frequency of 48.7% and greater than 6 whorls with associative frequency of 51.20% were present with no important disparity (Table-1); but, in the Group-2, findings of X^2 tests ($X^2 = 0.4160$) between patterns of six whorls having comparative frequency of 47.4% and greater than six whorls with comparative frequency of 52.50% displayed an important disparity. In the Group-3, the findings of X^2 test ($X^2 = 61.8210$) between patterns of six whorls with comparative frequency of 27.50% and greater than whorls with comparative frequency of 72.40% also displayed an important disparity (Table-1). There was a significant disparity between Group-1 and 2 and Group-2 and 3 but no disparity between Group-1 and 2 (Table-1).

Table I - Frequency Distribution of Digital Patterns of Patients

Total		Group - 3 (Controls)		Group - 2 (High Risk Females)		Group - 1 (Breast Cancer Patients)		Whorl Subtype
%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	
37.80	233.0	27.50	85.0	47.40	73.0	48.70	75.0	Whorls 6
62.10	383.0	72.40	223.0	52.50	81.0	51.20	79.0	Whorls < 6
100.00	616.0	100.00	308.0	100.00	154.0	100.00	154.0	Total
27.4520		61.8310		0.4160		0.1040		Test Result
2		1		1		1		df
P<0.0500		P<0.0500		Not Significant		Not Significant		x ²

There was pattern's highest frequency in Digit-1 (thumb of right hand) which was loop with comparative frequency of 45.70% and minimum was tented arch with comparative frequency of 0.90% ($X^2 = 17.47\%$). In Digit-2 (forefinger of the right hand) the maximum frequency of 41.80% and minimum frequency was incidental loop with comparative frequency of 0.90% ($X^2 = 21.2830$). The maximum and minimum pattern's frequency in Digit-# (middle finger of the right hand) were loop and accidental loop as 65.40% and 0.40% correspondingly. In Digit-4, the maximum and minimum frequency of the pattern was true whorl and twinned loop as 46.70% and 0.10% ($X^2 = 3.9770$). In Digit-5 (little finger of right hand), highest and lowest frequency of patterns was loop and tented arch as 71.20% and 0.10% ($X^2 = 27.8680$).

In Digit-6 (thumb of the left hand), highest and lowest pattern's frequencies were loop and accidental loop with comparative frequencies of 53.80% and 0.30% ($X^2 = 22.5260$) correspondingly. In Digit-7 (forefinger of left hand), highest and lowest pattern frequencies were loop and accidental loop with comparative frequencies of 38.60% and 0.80% correspondingly ($X^2 = 26.1890$). In Digit-8 (middle finger of left hand), highest and lowest frequencies were loop and accidental loop with comparative frequencies of 85.20% and 0.40% correspondingly ($X^2 = 40.3560$). In Digit-9 (ring finger of the left hand) highest and lowest frequencies were loop and lateral pocket loop with comparative frequencies of 44.80% and 0.40% correspondingly ($X^2 = 28.18$). In Digit-10 (little finger of the left hand), highest and lowest frequencies were loop and tented arch with comparative frequencies of 71.50% and 0.40%, the outcome of predictive test values in the digits between studied patterns displayed a significant disparity ($X^2 = 21.3330$).

DISCUSSION:

With the increase of the population in the world, it is very important to develop methods and procedures to diagnose the persons with the risk factors of any disease or already having that disease in a cost effective way without losing the care quality in health care service. The utilization of the digital dermatoglyphics as appeared in this research work is a rather unique method and cost-efficient for the diagnoses of such kind of patients. While investigating the dermatoglyphics and patients of cancer in general, other research works have examined an increase in the whorls in 200 and 390 female patients accordingly.

In one other research work, patients suffering from various cancers displayed whorls to be available and whereas examining patients with high risk present with more whorls and a high amount of the loops in the patients of the cancer. Additionally, genetic assessment of the breast cancer proposed that an enhanced susceptibility to this complication was, hereditary as autosomal leading allele with great penetrance among females. Hereditary and ancestral complication of the breast cancer are well known entities. The research works precisely associated to the correlation between subtypes of digital whorl and incidence of breast cancer. It has confirmed the statistically important disparity of the availability of six or more digital whorls out of ten in the patients suffering from breast cancer and females present with the high risk in comparison to the females of the control group. It is very amazing that in this current research work, we discovered a significant disparity of the availability of the whorl sub-types less than six out of ten digits, between Groups-1 and Group-3 and Group-2 and Group-3 but not between the Group-1 and Group-2.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of the research work demonstrated that the availability of six or high whorls has association with the complication of the breast cancer. In future, dermatoglyphic pattern will be very helpful in the identification of females present with the high risks to develop the disease of breast cancer to prevent it with timely treatment.

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